

Management Principles: A Case Study on the Impacts of Leadership Styles on Business Sustainability

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ARTICLE INFORMATION	ABSTRACT
<p>Article history: Published on 9th Dec 2025</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords: Management Management Principles Leadership Styles Business Sustainability</p>	<p>This paper reviews management principles with a focus on the leadership styles on business sustainability. Specifically, the paper looks at how commonly identified leadership styles (Autocratic vs Democratic; Bureaucratic vs Laissez-faire; Transformational vs Transactional; and Servant style) influence success of an organization. The paper highlights the importance of sustainability to the organizational management, ranging from gaining support from beneficiaries, negotiating favorable contracts with suppliers and vendors, getting favorable treatment from government authorities to protection of stakeholders' health, properties safety, and the environment.</p>

1. Introduction

Effective leadership is a key factor in a life and success of an organization as it transforms potentials into reality. There is no specific definition of leadership since leadership is complex and because it is studied in different ways that require different definitions. Many theorists have emphasized leaderships in deferent perspectives depending the varieties of situations and environments. Many of these definitions have based on the phenomena such as traits, behaviour, influence, interaction models, role relationships, and occupation of an administrative position (Yukl, G., and Falbe, C.M. 1990). Common known theorists are like Fredrick Taylor who worked on Scientific Management, Max Weber who worked on bureaucratic leadership, Mary P. Follett who worked on Participatory Management, McGregor who discussed two leadership theories (theory x and y) and Luther Gulick who worked on Principles of Management (POSDCORB). The midpoint of all these theorists was to find out "What essentially leadership style/approach works best for organization".

Leadership is the ultimate act which brings to success all of the potent potentials that is in organization and its people (IAAP, 2009). Leadership as defined by Barnard 1938 in IAAP, (2009), is the ability of superior to influence the behaviors of subordinates and pursued them to follow a particular course of action. Kouzes J.M, Posner B.Z, (2007) defined leadership as a major way in which people change the mind of others and move organization forward to accomplish identified goals of the organization. These authors above, with others came up to the conclusion of those styles of leadership we are going to discuss in the below passage.

2. Styles of Leaderships

There are several number of different approaches, or 'styles' to leadership and management that are fundamentally have different assumptions and theories. The style that individuals use will depend on the assortment of their beliefs, values and preferences, as well as the organizational culture and norms which will encourage some styles and discourage others (Kendra Cherry, Leadership Styles, at <http://psychology.about.com/od/leadership/>). Commonly identified styles are: Autocratic vs Democratic; Bureaucratic vs Laissez-faire; Transformational vs Transactional; and Servant style of Leadership.

2.1 Autocratic Leadership Style

Autocratic leadership, also known as authoritarian leadership, which is a leadership style distinguished by individual control over all decisions and earns little input from group members. Autocratic leaders normally make decisions based on their own ideas and judgments, and rarely accept advice from followers. Autocratic leadership involves absolute (Kouzes J.M, Posner B.Z, 2007, Kendra Cherry,).

However, in some circumstances this style of leadership is effective to use when there is New, untrained staff do not know which tasks to do or Staff do not respond to any other leadership style. It may also used when there is limited time in which to make a decision (Kouzes J.M, Posner B.Z, and 2007).

2.2 Democratic Leadership Style

Conversely to autocratic leadership, democratic leadership, also is identified as participative leadership, is a type of leadership style in which members of the group take a more participative role in the decision-making procedures. Researchers have found that this learning style is usually one of the most successful and lead to higher productivity, better contributions from group members, and increased group morale (Kouzes J.M, Posner B.Z, 2007, Kendra Cherry,). This style is more successful when used with highly skilled or experienced employees or when implementing operational changes or resolving individual or group problems. However, this style of leadership is commonly subject to much time consuming and treats the leader as challenged or opposed by the staff on his/her decisional views.

Characteristics of Autocratic vs Democratic
(Kouzes J.M, Posner B.Z, 2007, Kendra Cherry)

Autocratic	Democratic
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Staff expected to obey orders without receiving any explanations • Manager retains as much power and decision-making authority as possible • Does not consult staff, nor allowed to give any input • Rely on threats and punishment to influence • Do not trust staff • Leader always says “Do what I say” 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Encourages staff to be a part of the decision making • Keeps staff informed about everything that affects their work and shares decision making and problem solving responsibilities • Allows staff to establish goals • Encourages staff to grow on the job and be promoted • Recognizes and encourages achievement • Leader says “Lets agree on what we do”

2.3 Bureaucratic

Bureaucratic leadership is where the manager handles administrative and managerial issues by the book roles, principles and procedures. Everything must be done according to procedures or policies laid down (Kouzes J.M, Posner B.Z, 2007, Kendra Cherry). If it isn't covered by the book, the managers make reference to the next level above him or her. This manager is really more of a police officer than a leader. He or she reinforces the rules.

2.4 Laissez-faire (Delegative leadership)

Laissez-faire leaderships offer little or no guidance to the members and leave decision-making up to group members. All authority or power is given to the staff and they would be the one who determine goals, make decisions, and resolve problems on their own (Kendra Cherry, at <http://psychology.about.com/od/leadership/>). This style is more effective where staff are capable and motivated to work. While this style can be useful in circumstances that involve highly qualified experts, it often leads to poorly defined roles and a lack of motivation. It is noted that laissez-faire leadership tends to result in groups that lack direction, where members blamed each other for mistakes, refused to accept personal responsibility, and produced a lack of progress and work (Kouzes J.M, Posner B.Z, 2007, Kendra Cherry).

Characteristics of Laissez-faire (Delegative leadership) vs Bureaucratic

Laissez-faire	Bureaucratic
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The manager gives little or no direction and gives staff as much freedom as possible • Authority or power is given to the staff • Staff must have been highly skilled, experienced, and educated • Is used where staff are capable and motivated to work • Staff have pride in their work and the drive to do it successfully on their own • Often have poorly defined roles 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Employees are performing routine tasks over and over. • Employees must understand standards or procedures. • Training on equipment and procedures to operate tasks must be given to offer safety or security of the staff • Employees are doing tasks that require handling cash. • Staff do only what is expected of them and no more

2.5 Transformational leadership

Transformational leadership observes leadership in a different way. It perceives a right leader as one who can refine the values, hopes and needs of group into a vision, and then encourage and empower them to perform that vision (Kouzes J.M, Posner B.Z, 2007). Transformational leaders as defined by Purushothaman in TAU handout are charismatic. Charisma refers to a behavior leaders demonstrate that inspire confidence, commitment, and admiration the toward leader. In this matter, combines charisma, inspirational leadership, and intellectual stimulation drive leader towards the set organizational goal. Kouzes J.M, Posner B.Z, (2007) says Transformational leadership plays special and critical roles in the revitalization of existing businesses of the organizations. The Transformational leader develops new visions for the organization and mobilizes employees to accept and work toward attaining these visions (Dubrin J. A, 2010). According to this author, transformational leadership starts with the

development of a vision, a view of the future that will stimulate and convert potential followers. This vision may be developed by the leader, by the senior team or may emerge from a wide series of discussions. The important factor is the leader buys into it, hook, line and sinker (Dubrin J. A, 2010). While a transactional leader thinks of improvement or development as doing the same thing better: an organization that get in touch with more people, a company that makes more money, a transformational leader thinks about changing the world, even if only on a small scale (Kouzes J.M, Posner B.Z, 2007).

2.6 Transactional Leadership

In Transactional Leadership, controlled social systems work best with a defined series of rules and command. People are motivated by reward and punishment rather than encouragement and empowerment. When people have agreed to do a job, a part of the deal is that they concede all authority to their manager for implementation. The chief purpose of a subordinate is to do what their manager tells them to do (Kouzes J.M, Posner B.Z, and 2007).

The transactional leader works all the way through creating clear structures required of their subordinates, and the rewards that they get for following orders. Punishments are not always priority, but they are well-understood and formal to the followers, so for this reason, all the systems of discipline are usually in place (Kouzes J.M, Posner B.Z, and 2007).

Characteristics of Transformational vs Transactional leadership

Transformational	Transactional
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • People will follow a person who inspires them. • Align person with vision and passion to achieve great things. • The way to get things done is by injecting enthusiasmand energy. • Creates and sustains an environment that maximizes human and organizational capabilities 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • People are motivated by reward and punishment. • Social systems work best with a clear chain of command. • When people have agreed to do a job, they concede all authority to their manager for implementation. • The chief purpose of a subordinate is to do what their manager tells them to do. • Emphasizes getting things done within the umbrella of the status quo

2.7 Servant leadership

Similarly to other leadership style, many authors believe that the fundamental mission of leader is to serve the needs of the their constituents, including employees, customers, and communities. They measure their effectiveness in terms of their ability to help others. This is what Dubrin J. A, (2010) defines a servant leaders as they exhibit concern about the needs of their constituents; they usually show qualities such as patience, honesty, good listening skills, and appreciation of others. As in practical ground where leader seeks the individuals to recognition him/her as leader, a servant leaders see themselves as working for members and recognize subordinates as valuable entity. Another defining characteristic of servant leaders is their high level of integrity .The servant leader uses his or her talents to help group members (Dubrin J. A, 2010). For example, if the leader happens to be a good planner, he engages in planning because it will help the group attain its goals. The big assumption of Servant leaders is that, "servants first" with the object of ensuring that other people's highest priority needs are being served (Kouzes J.M, Posner B.Z, 2007).

3. The Leadership Style of Indra Nooyi

Indra Krishnamurthy Nooyi (Nooyi) as documented in this case by several editors, was the most powerful women leader in the contemporary leadership ranked Number 3 in the world. She possessed her ability of leadership through different posts she held in the company since her first appointment of being a leader of the company. As Senior Vice President (SVP) of the company, Nooyi was able to initiate business strategic decisions of the company to defeat other competitors. When she was promoted as PepsiCo's Chief Financial Officer (CFO), she was able to innovate different functions of the company on the areas of finance, procurements, investor relations, strategy, and information technology. In these fields, Nooyi seems successful as her measures prevented the company from slowing-down. With her effort as CFO, the company was able to increase its annual revenue, and due to this, she was promoted as the Chief Executive Officer (CEO).

When Nooyi was appointed as Chief Executive Officer (CEO), her new roles were able to improve and sustain the company thus opening the company to the global business. As CEO, she continued showing leadership stability by underpinning the company vision of "Performance with Purpose."

On my point of view, Nooyi was a good leader, strategic leader, courageous leader with focus of the company future, a purposeful Leader who shares with others a common goal of the company for the benefit of the company. Despite the existing variation, the Nooyi's leadership would not be challenged on the basis of gender differences. She exhibited all the features of good leader that any leader of any gender could have exhibited. To me, gender issue has no strong point in leadership outcome. This is significant in the Nooyi's ability to lead this company. This ideal is supported by the study done by Kouzes J.M, Posner B.Z, (2007); "Male and female leaders are equally effective; effectiveness most often depend upon the fit between the setting and the management gender". However, Ealy and Johnson 1990 in Kouzes J.M, Posner B.Z, (2007) commented that women have been found to practice more democratic, more encouraging participation as compared to men who are more autocratic and directing performance.

Nooyi seems to apply Contemporary Approaches to Leadership of both transformational and transactional leaderships. She aligns organizational vision, employee goals with the leader's goals as described by Purushothaman in TAU handout. She demonstrated a transactional leadership approach as she set several strategic plans and procedures of the company for the employees to follow. This is typical feature of transactional leadership as described by (Purushothaman in TAU handout, 2015), Kouzes J.M, Posner B.Z, 2007)

4. The Importance of Sustainability in the Management of a Company

Sustainability has become a more and more integral part of doing business in any rival industry. Bertels S, (2010), says that, for the companies to balance their financial business, social and environment risks, obligations and opportunities, sustainability must move from the being an add on to "just the way we do things around here". As per this author, organizational leaders must recognize the culture of organization they lead.

Colbert, B. and Kurucz, E. (2007), defines sustainability as continuation of organizational survival throughout in the arena of delivery of its business and services in the manner that satisfies the users. For an organization, it means that it has the elements necessary to carry on and continually enhance its activities in pursuit of a defined mission. It thus has both a defined mission and some combination of goals and objectives, the accomplishment of which ensures the successful pursuit of the mission. (Colbert, B. and Kurucz, E. 2007).

Though many authors consider sustainability as mainly about organizations financially self-reliant, Coblenz, J. B. (2002), views it as long term planning, competent and sufficient management and staff, visionary leadership, staff obligation to the organization's mission, grantsmanship skills, networking skills, an ongoing strategic planning process and a positive attitude among staff, they know what resources are available, or potentially so, how they will trail them, and constantly seek diversified funding sources as they focus on their mission in all that they do. In the different literature, some of the importance of sustainability to the organizational management have been discussed in detail and few of them are: Gaining support from beneficiaries; Negotiating favorable contracts with suppliers and vendors; Getting favorable treatment from government authorities; Protection of stakeholders' health, properties safety, and the environment

4.1 Gaining support from beneficiaries

The beneficiaries from the company are those all stakeholders who take part in the company in one way or another. They range from all management team, employees, suppliers, sellers, customers, sponsors, investors, government and community at large Wales T, (2013). These have big valuable roles in supporting the company in term of materials and ideas. This is more impact when the company significantly addresses its sustainability strategies through planning, competent and sufficient management and staff, visionary leadership, staff commitment to the organization's mission, networking skills, and a positive attitude among staff (Coblentz, J. B. 2002).

According to Susan A. M and Worley C. G, Sustainability and effectiveness of the organization should address the needs and preferences of many external and internal stakeholders. Leading companies should create rich Inter-organizational network connections that accelerate and enhance the scale of the transition to sustainable functioning. Their heavy engagement and interactions with external stakeholders redefines the boundaries of the company (Susan A. M and Worley C. G).

Structured Sustainability guarantees future security of the shareholders of their investment and services offered by the company. Colbert and Kurucz (2007) argue that shareholders may in fact be a drivers, rather than a barriers to a more sustainable approach to business, highlighting the shifting nature of the business/society relationships, social services that the company delivers. Despite the fact that some times the company may fall into recession, there are still some expectations and pressures from some shareholder groups for more support, sustainable/ethical investment opportunities, and significant pressures in relation to their value shares (Colbert and Kurucz, 2007).

4.2 Negotiating favorable contracts with suppliers and vendors

Many suppliers and vendors are more pessimistic about unreliable future outcome of their business acquaintances that may have negative impact to their business advancement. They prefer to work with those counterparts with a promising potential long term profit. A company with a precious strategic sustainability in place can easily negotiate with any supplier and vendor on any item/product it requires. This will be true if we cite the author Polman P, CEO, Unilever (in CIPD, 2012) who said, unless the benefit shared between companies engaging into negotiation persists for years in an equitable value, then investment would result in a favorable state of affairs. This will in turn incorporate the entire element of Supply Chain Management (SCM).

4.3 Protection of stakeholders

Sustainability protects stakeholders' health, properties safety, and the environment.

The organizations with strategic sustainability in place are those normally committing themselves to take long term measures to protect the health of their stakeholders together with their properties. Pojasek R.B (2010) argued that, in a sustainable organizations, the leaders should stress responsibility to keep the public, their ethical aspects, and the need to practice a good citizenship to ensure that the public health, safety, and the environment is protected. The scope of this protection includes not only relating to operations, but also the full life cycle of their properties, products and services. This author continue emphasize that, a sustainable organization should call attention to resource conservation and waste reduction and have a planning that anticipate adverse impacts to the public health coming from production, distribution, transport, use, and disposal of products.

4.4 Getting favorable treatment from government authorities

The roles of government towards any organization, public or non-governmental (NGO), profit or nonprofit in many countries is to set the policies and standards of conduct to protect the public. The government also benefits from organizations for services delivered to their public. In other hand, the government collects the revenues from profit making organizations. For these reason the government is fully concern with organizational sustainability in that it should assures these policies and standards are not violated.

For all the organizations that meet those policies and standards for sustainability in many instances would be granted permission to conduct their businesses while protected and facilitated by government in many countries. Some may be supported by government trough financial grants when fall in recession.

5. Conclusion

Though there is no specific definition of leadership, many author have come to the concurrence argument that leadership is the ultimate act which brings to success all of the potent potentials that is in organization and its people. The commonly identified styles of leadership are Autocratic vs Democratic, Bureaucratic vs Laissez-faire, Transformational vs Transactional and Servant. In the case above, Nooyi seems to be a good leader, strategic leader, courageous leader with focus of the company future, a purposeful leader who shares with others a common goal of the company for the benefit of the company. She seems to focus on the sustainability of the organization. The importance of sustainability to the organizational management have been discussed in detail ranging from gaining support from beneficiaries, negotiating favorable contracts with suppliers and vendors, getting favorable treatment from government authorities to protection of stakeholders' health, properties safety, and the environment .

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